

ESTIMATION OF BISMUTH. PART II. TURBIDIMETRIC ESTIMATION WITH BROMATE-BROMIDE MIXTURE

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Small quantities of Bi (10^{-4} – 10^{-6}) have been estimated with bromide-bromate mixture in a Zeiss turbidimeter with the filters 533.

Bismuth was estimated and separated from lead, copper, zinc, cadmium, etc., by hydrolysis with bromate-bromide mixture by Moser and Maxymowicz (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1925, **67**, 248). They observed that very small quantities of bismuth can be detected turbidimetrically by the above mixture. This method is more sensitive than the one using sodium sulphide with gum acacia or polyvinyl alcohol as the peptiser (Kurthy and Müller, *Biochem. Z.*, 1924, **149**, 225; Yamamoto, *Bull. Inst. Phys. Chem. Research, Japan*, 1937, **16**, 1312). A marked opalescence was obtained even in so dilute solutions in which the sulphide produced practically no colouration.

The author of the present paper has observed that very small quantities of bismuth even up to the order of 10^{-6} g. can be estimated turbidimetrically.

The turbidity produced when a bromate-bromide mixture was added to a bismuth solution, was measured in a Zeiss Turbidimeter with the filter S 53. Since no selective colour was measured, the wave-length of the filter was not of any particular importance. Wave-length to which the eye was sensitive, was selected.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

In these experiments only the reagent quality chemicals were used.

Bismuth subnitrate was dissolved in water containing a few c.c. of nitric acid. From a measured volume of this solution the bismuth content was determined by the oxide method (Miller and Van Dyke Cruser, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, **27**, 1116). Solutions, containing different quantities of bismuth per c.c., were prepared by dilutions of a definite volume of this solution. The nitric acid content of these solutions should be kept low either by evaporation of the solution or by neutralisation with sodium carbonate, to avoid generation of bromine the colour of which will affect the analytical results.

Procedure.—A measured volume of the bismuth solution, so prepared, was diluted with water to 20 c.c. in a Jena bottle. To the solution was added quickly 10 c.c. of a bromate-bromide mixture (2.5 g. of KBr and 2.5 g. of KBrO_3 in 100 c.c.). The total volume was maintained at 30 c.c. After the addition of the reagent the bottle was shaken for a minute and then allowed to stand for 30–45 minutes when the quantity of bismuth was of the order of 10^{-4} – 10^{-5} g. and for 3 hours and a half when the quantity of bismuth was of the order of 10^{-6} g. The solution was then taken in the bottle of the turbidimeter and the turbidity, with the filter S 53, was measured against one of the discs, by rotating the right drum, keeping the left drum always at 100. The readings thus obtained with different solutions were plotted against their respective concentrations (Figs. 1–4). From these standard curves the amount of bismuth in an unknown sample was determined. During the measurement with the unknown solution the same disc and the same filter were used.

FIG. 1

Measured after $\frac{1}{2}$ — $\frac{3}{4}$ hr. against disc 4

FIG. 2

Measured after 1— $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. against disc 4

FIG. 3

Measured after $\frac{1}{2}$ — $\frac{3}{4}$ hr. against disc 3

FIG. 4

Measured after 3 $\frac{1}{2}$ hrs. against disc 1

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